

1 **Augmented-Reality neurorehabilitation in outpatient physical therapy for**
2 **individuals recovering from stroke: protocol of a two-arm, crossover**
3 **randomized controlled trial implemented in the clinical pathway**

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16
17 **Abstract**

18 **Importance:** There is a need for an accessible, clinically prescribed exercise intervention, that
19 patients can perform at home, at their own pace and on their own schedule, decoupling therapy dose
20 from therapist time.

21 **Objective:** The objective of the present crossover randomized controlled trial (RCT) is to evaluate the
22 clinical feasibility and the effectiveness of the Strolll neurorehabilitation platform in post-stroke
23 individuals in a real-world clinical setting.

24 **Design:** This study is a two-arm, crossover RCT. The study consists of three assessment sessions,
25 spread out over 16 weeks. These assessment sessions demarcate a usual-care control period and a
26 Strolll intervention period in randomized order.

27 **Setting:** The study will be carried out in the Netherlands and implemented at multiple clinics.

28 **Participants:** 100 post-stroke individuals who are either in the late sub-acute or chronic phase
29 (Functional Ambulation Category 3-5).

30 **Intervention:** Strolll delivers neurorehabilitation exercises via augmented-reality (AR) glasses for
31 people with neurological disorders. The Strolll intervention consisted of two weeks of in-clinic
32 training followed by six weeks of remotely prescribed and managed use at home integrated with usual
33 care.

34 **Main Outcomes:** The main outcomes to evaluate the feasibility of Strolll are safety, adherence,
35 performance, acceptability and user experience (i.e., post-stroke individuals and their therapists). The
36 main outcomes to evaluate the effectiveness of Strolll are indicators of gait, balance, falls risk and
37 upper-limb functioning.

38 **Results:** Recruitment started in February 2026 and the last assessment session is expected in
39 December 2026.

40 **Conclusions:** This study with Strolll implemented in clinical practice of post-stroke individuals
41 represents a unique step towards examining the feasibility and effectiveness of remotely prescribed
42 and managed high-dose neurorehabilitation with AR in people's home environment.

43 **Relevance:** By situating this study within real-world outpatient physical therapy for post-stroke
44 individuals, the research moves beyond lab-controlled environments to address the practical
45 complexities of neurorehabilitation in daily life.

46 **Trial registration:** Overview of Medical Research in the Netherlands (OMON;
47 <https://www.onderzoekmetmensen.nl/en>), identifier NL-OMON58312

48

49 **Keywords (3-10):** stroke, augmented reality, gamified exercise, neurorehabilitation, clinical
50 feasibility, effectiveness.

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52

53 **1. Introduction**

54 Stroke is a significant healthcare problem¹. It is characterized as the acute onset of focal injury of the
55 central nervous system due to a cerebral blood circulation disorder, including ischemic and
56 hemorrhagic stroke. This can cause loss of neural function and central nervous system damage,
57 resulting in various disabilities². Motor impairments, such as hemiparesis, are one of the most
58 recognized post-stroke impairments, affecting about 80% of the patients³. It restricts activities and
59 participation in daily life⁴ and decreases functional independence^{4,5}. Other disabilities include
60 cognitive impairments such as unilateral spatial neglect (failure of perception/response towards
61 contralesional stimuli⁶), aphasia and limb apraxia⁷. To stimulate the recovery of these impairments
62 and improve the quality of life, rehabilitation is essential⁴.

63 Guidelines specific for post-stroke rehabilitation in subacute (from three to six months after
64 the onset of stroke) and chronic phases in individuals with mild to moderate impairments (according
65 to the National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale⁸) recommend 10 to 40 minutes of moderate-intensity
66 aerobic exercise for three to five days per week⁹. In addition, rehabilitation should focus on task-
67 oriented, repetitive, high-frequency training^{10,11}, preferably performed at home or in the patient's own
68 environment¹². Whereas exercises with many repetitions are important for facilitating
69 neuroplasticity¹³, doing these repetitions can become mundane over time, which can lead to lower
70 motivation and less engagement to perform such exercises¹⁴. Maintaining high levels of motivation in
71 post-stroke individuals appears to be important for successful stroke rehabilitation^{13,15}. Therapy is
72 mainly given in clinics, facing practical hurdles such as limited availability of healthcare professionals
73 and poor accessibility to therapy. This requires patients to travel to the therapist, which can be
74 fatiguing, costly and time-consuming. At the same time, aging societies are facing a care crisis, where
75 there are not enough healthcare professionals available to treat and monitor the number of (often
76 chronic) patients of today, let alone the growing future numbers. Thus, there is a need for an
77 accessible, adherable, clinically prescribed exercise intervention, that can be performed in the
78 patients' own environment, without the physical assistance and presence of a therapist.

79 A promising technology-based rehabilitation intervention is Strolll, a medically certified
80 augmented-reality (AR) multidomain neurorehabilitation platform with physical and cognitive
81 exercises, including gait, balance and upper-limb function, delivered via state-of-the-art AR glasses
82 for people with neurological disorders, such as stroke, Parkinson's disease, traumatic brain injury, and
83 multiple sclerosis (Figure 1). AR glasses have see-through lenses that allow for interaction with
84 holographic objects (i.e., holograms), while still being able to see the real-world environment. Strolll
85 incorporates key principles of motor learning and neurorehabilitation¹⁶, such as increasing difficulty,
86 task-specific practice, variable practice, feedback and promoting the use of the paretic (upper) limb¹⁷.
87 Exercises can be adapted to personal preferences and abilities while being performed in a meaningful
88 context, having the potential to target task-specific goals relevant to the patient. With the gamified
89 nature of the intervention (a.k.a., serious games for rehabilitation purposes¹⁸), exercises are more
90 enjoyable and engaging, which can contribute to high therapy adherence^{19,20}. Recently, the (clinical)
91 feasibility and efficacy of previous generations of the Strolll platform for improving gait, balance, and
92 falls risk have been examined in people with Parkinson's disease in a lab setting¹⁹ and in a pragmatic
93 clinical setting²⁰. These studies demonstrated that previous generations of Strolll are safe, adherable,
94 usable, acceptable and potentially effective for people with Parkinson's disease when used
95 unsupervised at home while being asynchronously managed by a researcher¹⁹ or a therapist²⁰.
96 Although found feasible and effective for people with Parkinson's disease^{19,20}, the clinical feasibility
97 and effectiveness of Strolll for improving clinical outcomes related to post-stroke symptoms remains
98 unknown. Therefore, the objective of the present crossover randomized controlled trial (RCT) is to
99 evaluate the clinical feasibility and effectiveness of Strolll in post-stroke individuals in a real-world
100 clinical setting. It is expected that Strolll is i) clinically feasible in terms of safety, adherence,
101 performance, acceptability, and user experience (i.e., both post-stroke individuals and their therapists)
102 and ii) effective for improving indicators of gait, balance, falls risk, and upper-limb functioning in
103 post-stroke individuals.

104

105
 106 **Figure 1.** Strolll neurorehabilitation exercises: Basketball (A), Puzzle Walk (B), Hot Buttons (C),
 107 Smash (D), and Mole Patrol (E).

108

109 **2. Methods**

110 **2.1 Study design**

111 This study is a two-arm, crossover RCT with a 1:1 allocation ratio. The study will be carried out in the
 112 Netherlands and implemented at multiple physical therapy, exercise therapy or rehabilitation clinics.

113 After enrollment, the study consists of three assessment sessions with standard clinical tests, spread

114 out over 16 weeks (Figure 2) that are performed in the clinic by an affiliated therapist. These
 115 assessment sessions demarcate a usual-care control period and a Strolll intervention period in

116 randomized order. After the baseline assessment session (T0; Figure 2), half of the participants will
 117 start with the eight-week usual-care control period while the other half will start with the eight-week

118 Strolll intervention. After eight weeks, both groups will undergo the midterm assessment session (T1;

119 Figure 2) after which the usual care group will complete the eight-week Strolll intervention while the

120 other group will continue with the usual-care control period, followed by the final assessment session

121 (T2; Figure 2). For the Strolll intervention, participants will undergo two weeks of in-clinic training

122 with Strolll supervised by their therapist to get familiar with the device and exercises and to receive
 123 instructions on how to use Strolll at home. Then, participants will start with the remotely prescribed
 124 and managed six-week Strolll intervention at home integrated with usual care. Recruitment of this
 125 study started in February 2026 and the last T2 assessment session is expected in December 2026.
 126

127

128 **Figure 2.** Schematic of the two-arm, crossover randomized controlled trial.

129

130 2.2 Participants

131 The aim is to include 100 post-stroke individuals who are either in the late sub-acute or chronic phase.

132 In order to be eligible to participate in the study, a participant must: be 18 years or older, have

133 proficiency of the Dutch language, have a time after stroke of more than 3 months (i.e., late sub-acute

134 or chronic phase²¹), and have a FAC of 3 (ambulator, dependent on supervision), 4 (ambulator,

135 independent level surface only) or 5 (ambulator, independent). Participants with a FAC score of 5

136 must still experience gait and/or balance impairments identified by their therapist. A potential

137 participant will be excluded from participation in the study if they have: a progressive neurological

138 disorders (e.g., PD) and/or orthopaedic problems seriously interfering with gait, balance, falls risk

139 and/or upper-limb functioning, insufficient physical capacity to comply with the (training) protocol

140 (e.g., frequent faller), severe cognitive impairments to understand instructions (as observed by the

141 researcher or therapist), or severe visual or hearing impairments (after corrective aids) limiting the
142 intended use of Strolll. In addition, uncontrolled epilepsy is a contraindication for use of Strolll.
143 People should also discuss with their therapist if they can participate when they use personal
144 implanted medical devices. During the study, participants are not allowed to participate in other
145 intervention studies.

146 Therapists will be trained in applying these inclusion and exclusion criteria for the selection
147 of eligible participants and are given instructions for the administration of the clinical tests of the
148 assessment sessions to ensure that all therapists will use the same methods. Therapists will also
149 receive instructions on how to use the AR glasses and the accompanying accessories (e.g., router and
150 insert lenses), how to perform the exercises of Strolll and how to use the web portal. They will take
151 the system home to practice with both Strolll and the web portal. After about two weeks of practicing,
152 the therapists and researchers meet again to discuss and resolve any problems. Furthermore, a
153 researcher will be present during the first in-clinic training session with a participant to support the
154 therapist when needed.

155

156 **2.3 Sample size calculation**

157 We will include a convenience sample of 100 participants over approximately 10 clinical sites,
158 focusing on the feasibility of Strolll in the clinical setting. This sample size will give the therapists of
159 the clinics enough experience with the Strolll platform and intervention to evaluate feasibility from a
160 therapists' perspective (e.g., usability, acceptability, safety). In addition, the study design also allows
161 all participants to experience Strolll to collect feasibility outcome measures from a large group, which
162 is useful considering the heterogeneous nature of stroke. To justify this sample size, a power analysis
163 was conducted using G*Power 3.1.9.7. To detect a small-to-medium effect size ($d_z=0.35$)²² with an
164 alpha error of 5%, 80% power and a two-tailed paired-samples *t*-test, the analysis indicated a required
165 sample size of $N=67$ participants. The small-to-medium effect size was selected as being clinically
166 relevant yet conservative enough to account for the expected variability in intervention effects within
167 the stroke population. We aim for 50 participants in each arm, thus 100 participants for a within-

168 subject comparison (of the intervention and control period), thereby being robust for potential
169 dropouts (i.e., a dropout rate of 5% is expected during the usual-care control period and 20% during
170 the Strolll intervention), including people that cannot take Strolll home for safety or proficiency of use
171 reasons (percentages were based on results of Hoogendoorn et al.²⁰).

172

173 **2.4 Procedures and outcomes**

174 **2.4.1 Participant enrollment: enrollment and informed consent**

175 Therapists will inform eligible post-stroke individuals about the study. Interested individuals can
176 either send their contact details via a study flyer or contact the research team directly. During initial
177 contact with a potential participant (Contact moment 1; Figure 3), a researcher will provide detailed
178 study information by telephone or another communication method that is preferred by the potential
179 participant. After this, the participant information letter will be sent to the potential participant by mail
180 or email. One week later, a researcher will follow up (Contact moment 2; Figure 3) to answer any
181 questions and to ask if he or she is willing to participate. If so, the researcher will check inclusion and
182 exclusion criteria. If the potential participant is voluntarily willing to participate and eligible, he or she
183 will be asked to sign the informed consent form, which will also be signed by the researcher. The
184 involved therapist will be notified that the participant can start with the RCT. Before commencing
185 with the baseline assessment, written informed consent must be given. If the potential participant isn't
186 eligible, he or she will be excluded from participation in this study.

187

188

189 **Figure 3.** Flowchart of the procedure of the two-arm, crossover randomized controlled trial.

190

191 **2.4.2 Randomization and blinding**

192 After informed consent is given, participants will be randomly assigned by the researcher to one of the
193 groups (Figure 3) using an automated, custom-made minimization algorithm written in MATLAB
194 with an allocation ratio of 1:1. To balance groups, the minimization procedure is based on the
195 following stratification factors: age, sex, time after stroke, and FAC score. The data for the
196 randomization will be entered in the algorithm by the researcher, after which the participant and
197 therapist will be informed about the resulting group allocation before the baseline assessment. Since
198 blinding is not possible, participants, therapists and researchers will not be blinded for group
199 allocation. Additionally, due to pragmatic reasons (e.g., limited size and time demands of the research
200 and clinical teams) there will be no blinded assessor for the clinical assessments to evaluate the
201 effectiveness of Strolll.

202

203 **2.4.3 Baseline assessment session (T0): characterization and effectiveness**

204 The baseline assessment session serves to characterize the study sample and to provide baseline
205 values for evaluating the effectiveness of Strolll (see also Table 1). Study parameters used to
206 characterize the participants are demographics (e.g., age, sex, time after stroke) and various tests and
207 questionnaires. The Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA)²³ and Saltin-Grimby Physical Activity
208 Level Scale (SGPALS)²⁴ will be administered in the clinic by the therapist. In addition, the outcomes
209 of the Cumulative Illness Rating Scale (CIRS)²⁵, Nottingham Extended Activities of Daily Living –
210 index (NEADL)²⁶, Falls Efficacy Scale International (FES-I)²⁷, and 8-week falls history will be
211 collected through (online) questionnaires. The NEADL, FES-I and fall history will also be
212 administered during the other assessment sessions to evaluate the effectiveness of Strolll. In addition,
213 to evaluate the effectiveness of Strolll for improving indicators of gait, balance, falls risk and upper-
214 limb functioning, the following standard clinical tests will be administered by the therapist: the
215 FAC²⁸, 10-meter walk test (10MWT)²⁹, Timed Up-and-Go test (TUG at comfortable and fast speeds
216 and with dual task)³⁰, Five Times Sit-to-Stand test (FTSTS)³¹, Mini Balance Evaluation Scale Test
217 (Mini-BESTest)³², and Motricity Index – Upper Extremity (MI-UE)³³.

218

219 **Table 1.** Overview of standard clinical tests and questionnaires during the assessment sessions.

		Assessment session		
		T0	T1	T2
Home	CIRS	X		
	NEADL	X	X	X
	FES-I	X	X	X
	Falls history	X	X	X
	Semi-structured evaluation questionnaire			X
Clinic	MoCA	X		
	SGPALS	X		
	FAC	X	X	X
	10MWT	X	X	X
	TUG	X	X	X
	FTSTS	X	X	X
	Mini-BESTest	X	X	X
	MI-UE	X	X	X

220 Abbreviations: CIRS = Cumulative Illness Rating Scale; NEADL = Nottingham Extended Activities of Daily
221 Living – index; FES-I = Falls Efficacy Scale International; MoCA = Montreal Cognitive Assessment; SGPALS
222 = Saltin-Grimby Physical Activity Level Scale; FAC = Functional Ambulation Category; 10MWT = 10-meter
223 walk test; TUG = Timed Up-and-Go Test; FTSTS = Five Times Sit To Stand Test; Mini-BESTest = Mini
224 Balance Evaluation Systems Test; MI-UE = Motricity Index – Upper Extremity.

225

226 **2.4.4 Usual-care control period**

227 The participants will not receive any additional training or instructions related to the intervention
228 during the usual-care control period (T0-T1 [group 1] or T1-T2 [group 2]; Figure 2). They will
229 continue with usual care and carry out their activities as normal. Usual care is defined as the standard,
230 real-world treatment participants receive from their therapist, which can be highly variable among
231 participants in terms of frequency, type (e.g., group sessions) and rehabilitation goals. There are no
232 restrictions regarding the usual care of the participants. An (online) questionnaire will be used to
233 document the type, duration and frequency of usual care participants receive.

234

235 **2.4.5 Strolll intervention**

236 **2.4.5.1 Supervised in-clinic training with Strolll**

237 The Strolll intervention (T1-T2 [group 1] or T0-T1 [group 2]; Figure 2) begins with supervised in-
238 clinic training, in which the therapist gives instructions and demonstrates the AR exercises to the
239 participant to make him or her familiar with the technology, the AR glasses (i.e., Magic Leap 2) and
240 the procedures. This also allows the therapist to evaluate safety aspects and select the appropriate
241 settings for the exercises. Strolll comprises five AR exercises, namely Basketball, Smash, Mole
242 Patrolll, Hot Buttons and Puzzle Walk (Figure 1), which can be adapted based on the physical
243 capabilities and rehabilitation goals of the user. After training in the clinic for one to maximally three
244 sessions in two weeks, the therapist evaluates if the participant is capable of using the technology
245 independently in a safe and suitable manner (Figure 3). If this is the case, the participant takes Strolll
246 home for 6 weeks and continues with the exercises, which are available daily as remotely prescribed
247 by the therapist. If the training at home is not considered safe or suitable by the therapist (e.g., high
248 risk of balance loss while doing the exercises), the intervention stops and no further assessment
249 sessions will be administered, which will be documented by the therapist.

250 To deliver the Strolll intervention, participants will use Magic Leap 2 AR glasses, selected for
251 their superior vertical AR field of view. For participants requiring vision correction, clinics will be
252 equipped with a complementary lens kit providing eight prescription insert lenses from -2.0 to +3.0. If
253 participant's specific prescription falls outside this standard range (e.g., due to complex optical
254 requirements), tailored insert lenses will be ordered.

255

256 **2.4.5.2 Independent use of Strolll at home**

257 During independent use at home, adherence, safety aspects (falls and other adverse events),
258 performance scores and exercise progression will be tracked by the therapist. Participants will be
259 instructed to use Strolll five days a week for 30 minutes per day, but therapists may adjust this to the
260 participant's capabilities. The exercises can be performed at various moments throughout the day in
261 so-called exercise snacks. Through the Strolll web portal (Figure 4), the therapist will remotely

262 prescribe the type of exercises, exercise duration and challenge. Since the exercises are
263 complementary in terms of aspects of physical functioning they intend to improve, the therapists are
264 advised to prescribe all exercises. However, the number of minutes spent on a game and the settings
265 per game can be determined by the therapist. This will be determined based on the rehabilitation goal
266 of the participant, which will be chosen and documented by the therapist. The exercise program will
267 be evaluated and adjusted weekly during telephone calls or in-person therapy sessions. Progress will
268 be assessed by combining information of the participant in combination with feedback from exercises
269 that is available in the web portal (Figure 4). During these contact moments, the therapist will also
270 discuss participant's performance and document any adverse events (i.e., safety flags). Hereafter, the
271 exercises will be prescribed for the upcoming week.

272 For each AR exercise, feedback of performance in terms of game-play performance metrics
273 (e.g., score based on number of moles spawned) and functional performance metrics (e.g., distance
274 walked) are given during the exercises derived from AR glasses data. Together with the number of
275 minutes per exercise these are logged in the web portal and provide insight into exercise performance
276 and adherence. Furthermore, the challenge score, derived from all settings per exercise, summarizes
277 the overall challenge of the exercises and changes therein over time. See Supplementary Material 1
278 for more details on the AR exercises and metrics.

279

280

281 **Figure 4.** Strolll web portal used to prescribe and adjust the exercise program (A) and for feedback on

282 how often and how well the prescribed exercise program is performed (B).

283

284 **2.4.6 Midterm and final assessment sessions (T1 and T2): effectiveness and clinical**
285 **feasibility**

286 The therapist will administer standard clinical tests of gait, balance, falls risk and upper-limb
287 functioning (i.e., FAC, 10MWT, TUG, FTSTS, Mini-BESTest, and MI-UE) during both the midterm
288 and final assessment sessions. Additionally, the participant will fill out the NEADL, FES-I and 8-
289 week falls history prior to the midterm assessment session using (online) questionnaires after the
290 usual-care control period (T1 in group 1 and T2 in group 2; Figure 2) or together with the researcher
291 after the Strolll intervention period during a telephone interview in which the acceptability and user
292 experience of Strolll is also discussed using the semi-structured evaluation questionnaire (T2 in group
293 1 and T1 in group 2; Figure 2). The latter is done to ensure comprehensibility and this procedure is
294 comparable to the one successfully used in a prior study with a previous generation of Strolll in
295 people with Parkinson's disease^{20,34}.

296 Clinical feasibility of the Strolll intervention according to the participants will be examined
297 with semi-structured evaluation questionnaires in terms of user experience (i.e., the User Experience
298 Questionnaire [UEQ]³⁵), technology acceptance and use (i.e., Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use
299 of Technology informed questions³⁶), top-3 barriers and facilitators of Strolll, and intervention-
300 specific questions regarding Strolll (see Supplementary material 2). In light of the potential future
301 implementation in the clinical pathway, therapists will also be asked about their experience with
302 Strolll through a purpose-made questionnaire after training their last participant, including how they
303 prescribed the intervention, a top-3 barriers and facilitators, technology acceptance and the UEQ (see
304 Supplementary material 2).

305

306 **2.5 Discontinuation or modification of allocated intervention**

307 Participants may withdraw from the study at any time for any reason without any consequences.
308 Alternatively, the researcher or therapist can decide to withdraw a participant from the study due to
309 urgent medical reasons. Participants who withdraw from the crossover RCT will not be replaced, as
310 the sample size calculation takes these dropouts into consideration. To minimize a potential bias in

311 user-experience outcomes, participants that drop out after using Strolll at home will be asked to
312 complete the semi-structured evaluation questionnaire.

313

314 **2.6 Premature termination of the study**

315 The study will be terminated prematurely if serious adverse events, such as injurious falls requiring
316 hospitalization, are reported by more than two participants when using Strolll. In accordance with
317 Dutch legal requirements, a liability insurance is in place, specifically article 7 of the Medical
318 Research Involving Human Subjects Act (in Dutch: Wet Medisch-wetenschappelijk Onderzoek met
319 Mensen, WMO). This insurance covers damage to research participants through injury or death as a
320 direct result of the study. The coverage applies to any damage that becomes apparent during the study
321 or within 4 years after the end of the study.

322

323 **2.7 Statistical analysis**

324 Data analysis will be performed in R (version 4.6.0 or newer) or JASP (version 0.19.3.0 or newer).
325 Missing data will be excluded analysis-by-analysis, if necessary.

326

327 **2.7.1 Feasibility**

328 Feasibility will be analyzed together for all people who completed (part of) the Strolll intervention at
329 home, independent of group. Safety will be described by the number of adverse events (i.e., falls,
330 dizziness, headache, and eyestrain), including a paired-samples *t*-test comparison of the average
331 weekly number of falls experienced during the usual-care control and Strolll intervention periods.
332 Adherence, performance and challenge scores will each be averaged over the first, second and third
333 part of the intervention at home, so approximately two-week intervals of Strolll intervention at home,
334 and analyzed descriptively to determine if the intervention is adherable and challenging-but-
335 achievable (i.e., aiming to balance task demands and capacity¹⁹). The UEQ outcomes will be
336 described descriptively and interpreted against known benchmark scores³⁷. All other usability and
337 acceptability outcomes, for both participants and therapists, will be processed descriptively.

338

339 **2.7.2 Effectiveness**

340 The effectiveness of Strolll for improving indicators of gait, balance, falls risk and upper-limb
341 functioning will be analyzed using linear mixed-effects models (LME). This method accounts for the
342 repeated structure of the design and handles potential missing data³⁸. The FAC, 10MWT, TUG,
343 FTSTS, Mini-BESTest, MI-UE, FES-I and NEADL following either the intervention (Strolll) period
344 or the control (usual care) period (i.e., values at T1 and T2 depending on group allocation), will be
345 analyzed using LME models with Intervention (usual care, Strolll intervention) as fixed effect, and
346 Participant specified as a random intercept as described in Twisk³⁹. Because participants can react
347 differently to the intervention due to differences in rehabilitation goals and heterogeneity in
348 symptoms, a diagnostic check will be performed in which a random slope is added to the model. In
349 addition, to analyze the possible modifying effect of the sequence, Sequence (group 1, group 2) and
350 the interaction between Intervention and Sequence will be added to the model as fixed effects. Since
351 this study does not include a wash-out period, carryover effects can be expected⁴⁰. To account for this
352 effect, we will also compare changes from T0 to T1 between groups, treating group 1 (usual care) as
353 the control group and group 2 (Strolll intervention) as the intervention group. LME models will be
354 used with Intervention as fixed effect, and Participant specified as a random intercept. Due to
355 randomization, no significant between-group differences are expected in baseline effectiveness
356 outcomes, which will be checked using independent-samples *t*-tests for continuous variables and Chi-
357 square tests for categorical variables.

358

359 **2.8 Role of the funding source**

360 The funder played no role in the design, conduct, and reporting of this study.

361

362 **3. Discussion**

363 The objective of this crossover RCT is to evaluate the clinical feasibility and the effectiveness of
364 Strolll, a medically certified AR multidomain neurorehabilitation platform for people with

365 neurological disorders. By situating this study within a real-world clinical pathway for outpatient
366 physical therapy in post-stroke individuals, the research moves beyond a lab-controlled environment,
367 addressing the practical complexities of neurorehabilitation in daily life and thereby improving the
368 generalizability of the study findings.

369 The crossover design is a strategic choice for several reasons. This design allows all
370 participants to receive the intervention and therefore gives therapists ample experience with the
371 intervention, leading to more elaborate feasibility outcomes from both participants and therapists.
372 Feedback on acceptability and user experience (e.g., barriers and facilitators) will give insight into the
373 implementation of Strolll in the clinical setting, which is important to better understand the uptake of
374 innovative technologies like AR. Often named challenges when trying to integrate such technologies
375 in usual care are limited high-quality evidence due to inadequate sample sizes and lack of information
376 on real-world efficacy⁴¹, challenges that this study will overcome by virtue of its design. Specifically,
377 strong points of this study in that regard are that the effectiveness is examined in a large group of
378 post-stroke individuals (N=100) in a real-world clinical setting involving approximately 10 clinics.
379 The broad inclusion criteria further increase the external validity of the study, as this group is
380 representative of the people seen in primary care practices. Strolll is versatile and can be used by
381 people who experience mild or severe limitations in motor and/or cognitive functioning, as exercise
382 settings can be tailored to the abilities of the individual and their rehabilitation goals. As a result, a
383 challenging and individualized exercise program can be created for all, which is an important driver
384 for optimal treatment benefits and broad implementation. The clinics participating in this study
385 represent early-adopter environments, providing a critical perspective for evaluating the feasibility of
386 Strolll. While these results will help in substantiating Strolll's potential in early-adopter clinical
387 environments, they also provide a necessary benchmark to determine the level of implementation
388 support (e.g., staff training) that will be required to ensure generalizability across a wider, more
389 diverse range of healthcare facilities.

390 This study focusses on home-based training as a future model of neurorehabilitation to
391 complement traditional therapy and scale the therapist workforce, where Strolll is integrated in usual
392 care. Because Strolll is a highly accessible intervention, we foresee people will be prescribed with a

393 higher treatment dose compared to usual care. In addition, because Strolll is an individualized,
394 gamified and remotely supervised intervention, we foresee that people adhere to the prescribed high-
395 dosage therapy at home as well. The latter expectation is supported by a recent study by Hoogendoorn
396 et al.²⁰ where participants mostly responded positively to the statement that "the fact that the therapist
397 can see remotely if I did my exercises at home motivates me to train"^{20,34}.

398 It is important to stress that digital health technologies and gamified rehabilitation like Strolll
399 are not intended to replace clinical decision making, clinical practice, and the skillset of a therapist, a
400 concern mentioned in previous studies with predecessors of Strolll by both people with Parkinson's
401 disease⁴² and therapists⁴³. Instead, digital health technologies serve as tools and platforms that
402 augment clinical practice, allowing for improved accessibility of care, higher therapy doses, better
403 treatment adherence and superior treatment effects⁴⁴.

404 The broadening of the medical label of Strolll from a Parkinson's disease specific intervention
405 to a broader neurorehabilitation population is a pivotal step for stroke treatment. While the motor
406 symptoms differ – Parkinson's disease being characterized by bradykinesia⁴⁵, and stroke by
407 hemiparesis and spasticity⁴⁶ - the underlying requirement for task-oriented, repetitive, and intensive
408 training is universal. This study with Strolll implemented in clinical practice of post-stroke individuals
409 therefore represents a unique step towards examining the feasibility and effectiveness of remotely
410 prescribed and managed high-dose gamified neurorehabilitation with AR in people's home
411 environment.

412

413 **4. Ethics statement**

414 The study will be conducted in accordance with the local legislation and institutional requirements.
415 Ethical approval has been obtained from the accredited Medical Ethics Committee United, the
416 Netherlands (R25.128, NL-010750). The trial has been registered on Overview of Medical Research
417 in the Netherlands (OMON; NL-OMON58312, published September 15, 2025). Protocol
418 modifications/amendments will be sent to the ethics committee for approval and updated in OMON.
419 Participants will provide their written informed consent obtained by the researchers DG, AD and CS

420 before participating in this study. Written informed consent was obtained from the individual for the
421 publication of the identifiable images.

422

423 **5. Data management**

424 Questionnaires and clinical tests collected in the clinic will be collected on paper and will be entered
425 into a digital database (i.e., Castor EDC). Digital copies and an export of the digital database will be
426 stored on a secure drive (i.e., Research Drive). Home questionnaires can also directly be entered into
427 the digital database by the participants using an online questionnaire. Personal data will be handled
428 according to the EU General Data Protection Regulation and the Dutch Act on Implementation of the
429 General Data Protection Regulation. Personal data to contact participants will be stored separately
430 from other data and provided with an ID number. An identification file with codes linking ID numbers
431 to participant numbers (four-digit codes) will be stored in a folder separate from the contact details
432 file with ID numbers. Files with personal data to contact participants and the identification file can
433 only be accessed with a password. Data collected on paper will be stored in a secured cabinet.
434 Administrative data (logbooks for data collection and analysis, manuals, protocols) will be stored on
435 OneDrive to improve interpretation and re-use of the data. All digital drives and databases require
436 multi-factor authentication.

437

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441

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444

445 **8. Conflicts of interest**

446 Melvyn Roerdink is a scientific advisor with share options for Strolll Ltd., a digital therapeutics
447 company building AR software for physical rehabilitation, for one day a week in addition to his main
448 positions as associate professor Technology in Motion at Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam and Senior
449 Scientist at Maastricht University. The remaining authors declare that the research was conducted in
450 the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict
451 of interest.

452

453 **9. Data availability statement**

454 The results of this study will be published in international peer-reviewed journals and will be
455 presented at national as well as international scientific conferences. Anonymized research data will be
456 published as supplemental material in publications or will be made available in a repository and/or
457 from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

458

459 **10. Supplementary material**

460 **Supplementary Material 1.** Detailed description of the Strolll exercises.

461 **Supplementary Material 2.** Semi-structured evaluation questionnaires.

462 **Supplementary Material 3.** SPIRIT checklist.

463 **Supplementary Material 4.** Informed consent forms.

464

465 **11. References**

- 466 1. Feigin VL, Brainin M, Norrving B, et al. World Stroke Organization (WSO): Global Stroke
467 Fact Sheet 2022. *International Journal of Stroke*. 2022;17(1):18-29.
468 doi:10.1177/17474930211065917
- 469 2. Sacco RL, Kasner SE, Broderick JP, et al. An Updated Definition of Stroke for the 21st
470 Century. *Stroke*. 2013;44(7):2064-2089. doi:10.1161/STR.0b013e318296aeca
- 471 3. Warlow C, van Gijn J, Dennis M, et al. *Stroke: Practical Management: Third Edition*. 2008.
- 472 4. Langhorne P, Coupar F, Pollock A. Motor recovery after stroke: a systematic review. *The*
473 *Lancet Neurology*. 2009/08/01/ 2009;8(8):741-754. doi:10.1016/S1474-4422(09)70150-4

- 474 5. Benjamin EJ, Blaha MJ, Chiuve SE, et al. Heart Disease and Stroke Statistics—2017 Update:
475 A Report From the American Heart Association. *Circulation*. 2017;135(10):e146-e603.
476 doi:10.1161/CIR.0000000000000485
- 477 6. Buxbaum LJ, Ferraro MK, Veramonti T, et al. Hemispatial neglect. *Neurology*.
478 2004;62(5):749-756. doi:10.1212/01.WNL.0000113730.73031.F4
- 479 7. Cramer SC, Richards LG, Bernhardt J, Duncan P. Cognitive Deficits After Stroke. *Stroke*.
480 2023;54(1):5-9. doi:10.1161/STROKEAHA.122.041775
- 481 8. Brott T, Adams HP, Olinger CP, et al. Measurements of acute cerebral infarction: a clinical
482 examination scale. *Stroke*. 1989;20(7):864-870. doi:10.1161/01.STR.20.7.864
- 483 9. Kim Y, Lai B, Mehta T, et al. Exercise Training Guidelines for Multiple Sclerosis, Stroke,
484 and Parkinson Disease: Rapid Review and Synthesis. *American Journal of Physical Medicine &*
485 *Rehabilitation*. 2019;98(7):613-621. doi:10.1097/phm.0000000000001174
- 486 10. French B, Thomas LH, Coupe J, et al. Repetitive task training for improving functional ability
487 after stroke. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. 2016;(11).
488 doi:10.1002/14651858.CD006073.pub3
- 489 11. Lee SH. *Stroke revisited: diagnosis and treatment of ischemic stroke*. Springer; 2017.
- 490 12. Langhorne P, Bernhardt J, Kwakkel G. Stroke rehabilitation. *The Lancet*. 2011/05/14/
491 2011;377(9778):1693-1702. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(11)60325-5
- 492 13. Kleim JA, Jones TA. Principles of Experience-Dependent Neural Plasticity: Implications for
493 Rehabilitation After Brain Damage. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*.
494 2008;51(1):S225-S239. doi:10.1044/1092-4388(2008/018)
- 495 14. Burdea GC. Virtual Rehabilitation – Benefits and Challenges. *Methods Inf Med*.
496 2003;42(5):519-523. doi:10.1055/s-0038-1634378
- 497 15. Oyake K, Suzuki M, Otaka Y, Momose K, Tanaka S. Motivational Strategies for Stroke
498 Rehabilitation: A Delphi Study. *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*.
499 2020;101(11):1929-1936. doi:10.1016/j.apmr.2020.06.007
- 500 16. Beek PJ, Roerdink M. Evolving insights into motor learning and their implications for
501 neurorehabilitation. In: Selzer ME, Clarke S, Cohen LG, Kwakkel G, Miller RH, eds. *Textbook of*
502 *Neural Repair and Rehabilitation: Volume 2: Medical Neurorehabilitation*. 2 ed. Cambridge
503 University Press; 2014:95-104.
- 504 17. Maier M, Ballester BR, Verschure PFMJ. Principles of Neurorehabilitation After Stroke
505 Based on Motor Learning and Brain Plasticity Mechanisms. *Frontiers in Systems Neuroscience*.
506 2019;13. doi:10.3389/fnsys.2019.00074
- 507 18. Michael DR, Chen SL. *Serious Games: Games That Educate, Train, and Inform*. Muska &
508 Lipman/Premier-Trade; 2005.
- 509 19. Hardeman LES, Geerse DJ, Hoogendoorn EM, Nonnekes J, Roerdink M. Remotely
510 prescribed and monitored home-based gait-and-balance therapeutic exergaming using augmented
511 reality (AR) glasses: protocol for a clinical feasibility study in people with Parkinson's disease. *Pilot*
512 *and Feasibility Studies*. 2024;10(1):54. doi:10.1186/s40814-024-01480-w
- 513 20. Hoogendoorn EM, Geerse DJ, van Dam AT, et al. Cueing-assisted gamified augmented-
514 reality home rehabilitation for gait and balance in people with Parkinson disease: feasibility and
515 effectiveness in the clinical pathway. *Physical Therapy*. 2026;106(3). doi:10.1093/ptj/pzag012
- 516 21. Bernhardt J, Hayward KS, Kwakkel G, et al. Agreed definitions and a shared vision for new
517 standards in stroke recovery research: The Stroke Recovery and Rehabilitation Roundtable taskforce.
518 *International Journal of Stroke*. 2017;12(5):444-450. doi:10.1177/1747493017711816
- 519 22. Cohen J. A power primer. *Psychological Bulletin*. 1992;112(1):155-159. doi:10.1037/0033-
520 2909.112.1.155
- 521 23. Nasreddine ZS, Phillips NA, Bédirian V, et al. The Montreal Cognitive Assessment, MoCA:
522 A Brief Screening Tool For Mild Cognitive Impairment. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*.
523 2005;53(4):695-699. doi:10.1111/j.1532-5415.2005.53221.x
- 524 24. Grimby G, Frändin K. On the use of a six-level scale for physical activity. *Scandinavian*
525 *Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports*. 2018;28(3):819-825. doi:10.1111/sms.12991
- 526 25. Linn BS, Linn MW, Gurel LEE. Cumulative illness rating scale. *Journal of the American*
527 *Geriatrics Society*. 1968;16(5):622-626. doi:10.1111/j.1532-5415.1968.tb02103.x

- 528 26. Nouri F, Lincoln N. An extended activities of daily living scale for stroke patients. *Clinical*
529 *Rehabilitation*. 1987;1(4):301-305. doi:10.1177/026921558700100409
- 530 27. Yardley L, Beyer N, Hauer K, Kempen G, Piot-Ziegler C, Todd C. Development and initial
531 validation of the Falls Efficacy Scale-International (FES-I). *Age and Ageing*. 2005;34(6):614-619.
532 doi:10.1093/ageing/afi196
- 533 28. Holden MK, Gill KM, Magliozzi MR, Nathan J, Piehl-Baker L. Clinical Gait Assessment in
534 the Neurologically Impaired: Reliability and Meaningfulness. *Physical Therapy*. 1984;64(1):35-40.
535 doi:10.1093/ptj/64.1.35
- 536 29. Collen FM, Wade DT, Bradshaw CM. Mobility after stroke: Reliability of measures of
537 impairment and disability. *International Disability Studies*. 1990;12(1):6-9.
538 doi:10.3109/03790799009166594
- 539 30. Podsiadlo D, Richardson S. The Timed "Up & Go": A Test of Basic Functional Mobility for
540 Frail Elderly Persons. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*. 1991;39(2):142-148.
541 doi:10.1111/j.1532-5415.1991.tb01616.x
- 542 31. Csuka M, McCarty DJ. Simple method for measurement of lower extremity muscle strength.
543 *The American Journal of Medicine*. 1985;78(1):77-81. doi:10.1016/0002-9343(85)90465-6
- 544 32. Franchignoni F, Horak F, Godi M, Nardone A, Giordano A. Using psychometric techniques
545 to improve the Balance Evaluation Systems Test: the mini-BESTest. *Journal of Rehabilitation*
546 *Medicine*. 2010;42(4):323-331. doi:10.2340/16501977-0537
- 547 33. Demeurisse G, Demol O, Robaye E. Motor Evaluation in Vascular Hemiplegia. *European*
548 *Neurology*. 2008;19(6):382-389. doi:10.1159/000115178
- 549 34. Geerse DJ, Hoogendoorn EM, van Doorn PF, et al. Cueing-assisted gamified augmented-
550 reality gait-and-balance rehabilitation at home for people with Parkinson's disease: protocol of a
551 pragmatic randomized controlled trial implemented in the clinical pathway. *Frontiers in Neurology*.
552 2025;16. doi:10.3389/fneur.2025.1512409
- 553 35. Laugwitz B, Held T, Schrepp M. Construction and Evaluation of a User Experience
554 Questionnaire. Springer Berlin Heidelberg; 2008.
- 555 36. Venkatesh VaM, Michael G. and Davis, Gordon B. and Davis, Fred D. User Acceptance of
556 Information Technology: Toward a Unified View. *MIS Quarterly*. 2003;27(3):425-478.
557 doi:10.2307/30036540
- 558 37. Schrepp M, Hinderks A, Thomaschewski J. Construction of a Benchmark for the User
559 Experience Questionnaire (UEQ). *International Journal of Interactive Multimedia and Artificial*
560 *Intelligence*. 2017;4(4):40-44. doi:10.9781/ijimai.2017.445
- 561 38. Krueger C, Tian L. A Comparison of the General Linear Mixed Model and Repeated
562 Measures ANOVA Using a Dataset with Multiple Missing Data Points. *Biological Research For*
563 *Nursing*. 2004;6(2):151-157. doi:10.1177/1099800404267682
- 564 39. Twisk JWR. *Analysis of Data from Randomized Controlled Trials: A Practical Guide*.
565 Springer Cham; 2021.
- 566 40. Lim C-Y, In J. Considerations for crossover design in clinical study. *Korean J Anesthesiol*. 8
567 2021;74(4):293-299. doi:10.4097/kja.21165
- 568 41. Yang J, Guan Z, Zeng D, et al. Extended reality in clinical neurology: From interdisciplinary
569 innovations to clinical practice. *Cell Reports Medicine*. 2026;102696.
570 doi:10.1016/j.xcrm.2026.102696
- 571 42. Hardeman LES, van Benten E, Hoogendoorn EM, et al. Home-Based Augmented Reality
572 Exercise For People With Parkinson Disease: Qualitative Acceptability Study. *JMIR Rehabil Assist*
573 *Technol*. 2025;12:e70802. doi:10.2196/70802
- 574 43. Hardeman LES, Hoogendoorn EM, van Benten E, Nonnekes J, Roerdink M, Geerse DJ.
575 Experiences and Perspectives of Home-Based Augmented Reality Gait-and-Balance Therapy Among
576 Parkinson's Therapists in the Dutch Healthcare System: Focus Group Study. *Zenodo*. 2026.
577 doi:10.5281/zenodo.18759823
- 578 44. Tosto-Mancuso J, Tabacof L, Herrera JE, et al. Gamified Neurorehabilitation Strategies for
579 Post-stroke Motor Recovery: Challenges and Advantages. *Current Neurology and Neuroscience*
580 *Reports*. 2022;22(3):183-195. doi:10.1007/s11910-022-01181-y
- 581 45. Bloem BR, Okun MS, Klein C. Parkinson's disease. *The Lancet*. 2021;397(10291):2284-2303.
582 doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(21)00218-X

583 46. Li S. Spasticity, Motor Recovery, and Neural Plasticity after Stroke. *Frontiers in Neurology*.
584 2017;8. doi:10.3389/fneur.2017.00120